

Thioamide Bands and Nature of Bonding in Complexes of Non-Transition and Non-Typical Transition Metals with Ethylene Thiourea

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Complexes of ethylene thiourea with As(III), Sb(III), Bi(III), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), and Sn(II) have been prepared and they have been investigated. As(III), Sb(III) and Bi(III) complexes are penta coordinated and are in most probability triangular bipyramidal in structure. Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Sn(II) complexes have probably tetrahedral structure. It has been found that the ethylene thiourea molecules are coordinated through sulfur.

ETHYLENE thiourea has been used as ligand by several workers¹⁻³. However much less work has been done with the complexes of ethylene thiourea with non-transition metals. Moreover, this ligand contains thioamide group $\text{H}-\overset{\cdot}{\text{N}}-\overset{\cdot}{\text{C}}=\text{S}$ in the ethylene thiourea ring. While carrying on work on the mode of linking of a thioamide group with metal ions and consequent effect on the four thioamide bands in infrared spectra, we had come to the conclusion that it is essential to consider the nature of shifting of all the four thioamide bands as well as changes in their intensities so that one may clearly infer whether the bonding is metal-sulfur or metal-nitrogen or simultaneous metal-nitrogen and metal-sulfur type in the complexes. Thus, the main aim of this paper is to show as to what are the changes in the positions and intensities of the four thioamide infrared bands on complexation with non-transition metal ions and non-typical transition metal ions. This aim has been tried to achieve by preparing complexes of As^{+3} , Sb^{+3} , Bi^{+3} , Zn^{+2} , Cd^{+2} and Hg^{+2} and recording the infrared spectra of the ligand and the complexes. The structural aspect and nature of metal-ligand bonding have also been examined herein.

Materials and Methods :

All chemicals used in this method was Analar quality or chemically pure grade.

Ethylene thiourea was prepared by the method of J. V. Allan⁴.

The complexes were prepared by the following methods :

(1) *Diethylene-thiourea Trichloro-antimony(III)* : $[\text{Sb}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_3]$:

2.285 g of SbCl_3 was dissolved in minimum volume of concentrated HCl and the resultant solution was diluted with ethanol. Care was taken that hydrolysis of SbCl_3 does not occur during dilution with ethanol. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was mixed in a filtered solution of 3.06 g of ethylene thiourea (ETU) in hot ethanol (100 ml). The mixture was refluxed on water bath at 85° . A clear golden yellow solution was formed after refluxing. The mixture was thereafter cooled when yellow precipitate of the complex, $[\text{Sb}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_3]$, precipitated out. It was filtered, recrystallised with ethanol and dried. It gave the following data on analysis :

Found : C, 17.2 ; H, 3.01 ; N, 12.9 ; Cl, 24.0 ;
Sb, 27.5%

Calcd : C, 16.7 ; H, 2.80 ; N, 12.4 ; Cl, 24.7 ;
Sb, 28.2%

(2) *Diethylene-thiourea Trichloro-bismuth(III)* : $[\text{Bi}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_3]$:

This was also prepared by method (1) mentioned above. BiCl_3 was used in place of SbCl_3 . Following analytical results were obtained :

Found : C, 13.4 ; H, 2.3 ; Cl, 20.4 ; Bi, 40.0%

Calcd : C, 13.7 ; H, 1.7 ; Cl, 20.5 ; Bi, 40.2%

(3) *Pentaethylene-thiourea Arsenic(III) Iodide Dihydroxide* : $[\text{As}(\text{ETU})_5\text{I}(\text{OH})_2]$:

This complex was prepared by refluxing a solution of 3.8 g freshly prepared AsI_3 in 50 ml ethanol with a solution of 3.06 g of ethylene thiourea in ethanol (100 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 4 hours at 85° on water bath. The yellow precipitate formed was filtered out and the filtrate on crystallisation gave red crystals of $\text{As}(\text{ETU})_5\text{I}(\text{OH})_2$.

Found : N, 18.75 ; I, 15.2 ; As, 9.40%
 Calcd : N, 18.76 ; I, 15.7 ; As, 10.05%

(4) *Diethylene-thiourea Dichloro-mercury(II)* :
 $[\text{Hg}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

This complex was prepared by simply mixing an ethanolic solution of 2.71 g HgCl_2 with an ethanolic solution of 3.06 g ethylene thiourea. The total volume of the mixture was 100 ml. A white precipitate of the complex was immediately formed. This was filtered out, washed with ethanol and dried at 110° in an electric oven.

Found : N, 10.77 ; Cl, 14.5 ; Hg, 42.0%
 Calcd : N, 11.78 ; Cl, 14.9 ; Hg, 42.1%

(5) *Diethylene-thiourea Dichloro-zinc(II)* :
 $[\text{Zn}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

1.4 g of ZnCl_2 in 50 ml ethanol was mixed with 2.0 g of ligand in 100 ml boiling ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for eight hours on sand bath. When it turned deep yellow, it was then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated on water bath and crystallised. The light yellow crystals of the complex was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried at 110° .

Found : C, 21.2 ; H, 3.5 ; N, 16.46 ; Zn, 18.5 ;
 Cl, 20.1%
 Calcd : C, 21.3 ; H, 3.7 ; N, 16.46 ; Zn, 19.1 ;
 Cl, 20.9%

(6) *Diethylene-thiourea Dichloro-cadmium(II)* :
 $[\text{Cd}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

This complex was prepared by refluxing a mixture of 1.8 g CdCl_2 in 20 ml conc. HCl and 2.0 g of ethylene thiourea in 50 ml ethanol. After refluxing the mixture on water bath at 85° for six hours, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate was crystallised when yellow complex precipitated out. These were filtered, washed with cold ethanol and dried at 110° .

Found : N, 13.89 ; C, 17.3 ; H, 3.7 ; Cd, 28.7 ;
 Cl, 17.8%
 Calcd : N, 13.03 ; C, 16.9 ; H, 3.9 ; Cd, 29.0 ;
 Cl, 18.3%

(7) *Aquodichloro monoethylenethiourea Sn(II)* :
 $[\text{Sn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}_2(\text{ETU})]$:

10 g of $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in minimum volume of conc. HCl by warming. 1.0 g of the ligand was also dissolved in 50 ml of hot ethanol. Both the solutions were filtered hot, mixed and refluxed for 4 hours on water bath at 85° . The yellow mixture was filtered and the filtrate was crystallised when light yellow crystals of the complex were formed. The crystals were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at 110° .

Found : N, 9.15 ; Cl, 22.5 ; C, 12.7 ; H, 2.4 ; Sn,
 37.6%

Calcd : N, 8.65 ; Cl, 23.0 ; C, 12.1 ; H, 2.3 ; Sn,
 38.4%

Infrared Spectra : The i.r. spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded in nujol mull in the range of $2000\text{-}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Magnetic Measurements : Magnetic moment measurement was done by means of Guoy Balance and all the complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

Results and Discussion

Microanalytical data of the antimony and bismuth complexes indicate their general stoichiometry to be $\text{M}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_2$. The stoichiometry of Zn, Cd and Hg complexes is $\text{M}(\text{ETU})_2\text{Cl}_2$. Sn forms 1 : 1 complex with ethylene thiourea having the empirical formula $\text{Sn}(\text{H}_2\text{O})(\text{ETU})\text{Cl}_2$ whereas As forms the complex with stoichiometry $\text{As}(\text{ETU})_2(\text{OH})_2$. Since most of these complexes are insoluble in common solvents, their molecular weights could not be determined.

Normal coordinate analysis of ethylene thiourea molecule was carried out by P. Bhaskara Rao and U. Agarwala³. As a result of a thorough investigation on this molecule, assignment of bands in the infrared spectra of this molecule was made. The major bands of interest of the ligand and the complexes with their assignments are shown in Table I.

It is well known that organic compounds containing a thioamide group $\text{H}-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$ give rise to four thioamide bands. On the basis of N.C.A. of ethylene thiourea, it has been proved that 1530 and 1505 cm^{-1} strong bands are the thioamide band I which have been split because of the presence of two thioamide groups in the ethylene thiourea molecule.

The 1200 cm^{-1} medium band in the spectrum of the ligand has major contributions from $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$, $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ and $\delta\text{N}-\text{H}$. The band III also gets split and are observed at 1040 cm^{-1} and 919 cm^{-1} and have contributions from $(\nu\text{CH}_2-\text{N} + \nu\text{C}-\text{C} + \nu\text{C}-\text{N})$ respectively while the band IV observed at 685 cm^{-1} as a medium band has contributions from $\nu\text{C}-\text{N} + \nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \text{ring deformation}$.

It has been reported by several workers that the thioamide band IV can be used as diagnostic for

TABLE 1—MAJOR IR BANDS OF INTEREST IN THE LIGAND THE COMPLEXES IN cm^{-1}

Compounds	Ligand	Complexes of E.T.U. with							Changes in Position	Changes in Intensity
		Sb	Bi	As	Zn	Cd	Hg	Sn		
Thioamide Band I $\delta\text{NH} + \delta\text{C}-\text{H} + \delta\text{CH}_2$	1530s 1506s	1546s 1525s	1540s 1516s	1540sh 1515sh	1544sh 1517s	1544sh 1512s	1544sh 1512s	1542sh 1525s	Blue shift	No change in intensity
Thioamide Band II $\nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \nu\text{C}-\text{N} + \delta\text{NH}$	1200m	1200w	1208w	1192	1196w	1192vw	1220 triplet splitting	1208w	No appreciable change in frequency	Considerable decrease in intensity
Thioamide Band III $\nu\text{C}-\text{C} + \nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \nu\text{CH}_2, -\text{N}$	1040s 919s	1030w 906m	1025w 904m	1037vw 912m	1033vw 917w	1029s 966w	1033w	1032vw 908vw	Red shift in frequency	Considerable decrease in intensity
Thioamide Band IV ($\nu\text{C}-\text{N} + \nu\text{C}=\text{S} + \text{Sym. ring deformation}$)	685m	650w	654w	669m	doublet centred at 656w	doublet centred at 654w	658w	650vw	Red shift	Decrease in intensity

metal-ligand bonding⁵⁻¹⁵. However, several other groups of workers including the present author¹⁶⁻¹⁹ have indicated that band IV alone cannot be used as a criterion for indicating whether coordination has taken place through S or through N or through both simultaneously. A clear idea of the nature of bonding between ligand and the metal ions can be derived from a study of the nature of change in the positions and intensities of all the four thioamide bands.

If the infrared spectra of the ligand and the present complexes are compared, changes in the positions and intensities of the thioamide bands are observed which are given in the Table 1. It is expected that the coordination of this ligand to the metal ion should take place through sulfur. This seems to be supported by the fact that the thioamide bands II, III and IV which have contributions from $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ have undergone either red shift or have decreased in intensity considerably or both have happened because of coordination of the ligand through sulfur. However, the thioamide band I have undergone blue shift. Had there been coordination through a N-atom of the ligand, red shift was expected.

Metal-ligand Vibrations : The far infrared spectra of the ligand in the range of 500 to 200 cm^{-1} have only few bands. These are at 375 and 335 cm^{-1} assigned to asymmetric ring deformation by Vaskara Rao⁸ on the basis of N.C.A. However new bands are observed in the infrared spectra of the complexes. These are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—FAR INFRARED BANDS IN THE INFRARED SPECTRA OF THE LIGAND AND THE COMPLEXES

Ligand	Ethylene thiourea complexes with							Assignments
	As	Sb	Bi	Zn	Cd	Hg	Sn	
375	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Assym. Ring deformation
335	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	Ring deform. + $\nu\text{C}-\text{S}$
—	504s	483s	342s	367s	362s	373s	325m	$\nu\text{M}-\text{Cl}$
—	329m	—	—	275m	258m	—	292w	$\nu\text{M}-\text{S}$

When the far infrared spectra of the complexes are compared with that of the ligand, it is found that new bands are observed in the spectra of the complexes which are not present in the spectrum of the ligand. Thus strong to medium new bands are observed in the spectra of As, Sb, Bi, Zn, Cd, Hg and Sn complexes at 504, 483, 342, 367, 362, 373 and 325 cm^{-1} respectively. Since metal-halogen stretching bands are strong²⁰ in the far infrared region, these bands may have contributions from $\nu\text{As}-\text{Cl}$, $\nu\text{Sb}-\text{Cl}$, $\nu\text{Bi}-\text{Cl}$, $\nu\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}$, $\nu\text{Cd}-\text{Cl}$, $\nu\text{Hg}-\text{Cl}$ and $\nu\text{Sn}-\text{Cl}$ respectively. The mass effect is clearly visible in these frequencies. In As, Sb, Bi, arsenic has the least atomic weight, hence the $\nu\text{As}-\text{Cl}$ has been observed at highest frequency and $\nu\text{Bi}-\text{Cl}$ at the lowest frequency among the three. In case of Zn, Cd and Hg, the mass effect has been observed by $\nu\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}$ and $\nu\text{Cd}-\text{Cl}$ but the $\nu\text{Hg}-\text{Cl}$ is larger than the $\nu\text{Cd}-\text{Cl}$ and $\nu\text{Zn}-\text{Cl}$ probably because of the fact that the Hg-Cl bond strength is comparatively larger. This is within our expectation because of the increasing electropositive nature of Zn, Cd and Hg. The $\nu\text{Sn}-\text{Cl}$ frequency is less than $\nu\text{Sb}-\text{Cl}$ although both have nearly equal atomic weights. This may be probably because of the weaker Sn-Cl bond strength as compared to Sb-Cl bond. Although these bands have main contributions from metal-chlorine stretching modes but some contribution from ring vibration cannot be overlooked.

In addition to the metal-chlorine stretching bands, medium to weak bands are observed in the i.r. spectra of As, Zn, Cd and Sn at 329, 275, 259 and 292 cm^{-1} . These may have contributions from $\nu\text{As}-\text{S}$, $\nu\text{Zn}-\text{S}$, $\nu\text{Cd}-\text{S}$ and $\nu\text{Sn}-\text{S}$ respectively. In case of Sb, Bi and Hg complexes, $\nu\text{M}-\text{S}$ band is not clearly visible up to 200 cm^{-1} . They probably fall below 200 cm^{-1} . The positions of $\nu\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{S}$ are in agreement with the previous works of a number of investigators²⁰⁻²¹ in this field of research.

On the basis of the stoichiometries and structures generally assumed by As, Sb and Bi complexes,

they may tentatively be assigned triangular bipyramidal structures whereas Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II) and Sn(II) complexes are most probably tetrahedral in structure.

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